

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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LANGUAGE-SKILL DIFFICULTIES AND STRATEGIC RESPONSES OF LOCAL EFL STUDENTS: A VISUAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract. The study investigates language-skill barriers and strategy use among EFL learners, with a special focus on the integration of visualization techniques into receptive and productive skills. A quantitative approach was employed using an online questionnaire consisting of demographic and 15 main items. The participants were 122 first-year English philology students from Termiz State University, Karshi State University, and Gulistan State University in Uzbekistan. The results showed that vocabulary limitations, misinterpretation of question types, and lack of coherence in writing were the most common challenges. Visualization-based strategies such as graphic organizers, pictorial aids, and model essay analysis proved effective in overcoming these difficulties. The findings highlight the pedagogical potential of visual techniques for enhancing learners' reading and writing performance.

Keywords: language-skill barriers; EFL learners; visualization techniques; receptive and productive skills; learning strategies; graphic organizers

Introduction / Literature Review

Learning strategies have long been regarded as central to the process of second language acquisition, as they equip learners with tools to facilitate comprehension and production. According to Ma (2009), strategies for grammar, vocabulary, and the four core language skills remain crucial for effective learning. Nation (2009) emphasizes that explicit training in reading and writing strategies significantly improves learner outcomes, while Staehr (2009) links vocabulary knowledge to advanced listening comprehension, underlining the interdependence of language skills.

Recent studies also show that learners face persistent challenges across receptive and productive domains. Hezam, Haidara, and Mohammed (2022) identify reading comprehension difficulties as one of the main obstacles for EFL learners, whereas Tovar Viera et al. (2024) report common problems in essay writing, including organization and coherence. At the same time, visualization techniques—ranging from graphic organizers to pictorial aids—have gained growing attention for their role in supporting memory, comprehension, and learner engagement in EFL contexts.

Results and Discussion

The findings revealed several recurring barriers that hindered the development of both receptive and productive skills among the participants. Vocabulary limitations were reported as the most frequent difficulty, which corresponds to Staehr's (2009) observation that insufficient lexical knowledge directly affects comprehension, particularly in reading and listening. Learners also indicated confusion in identifying question types, especially in reading tasks, which often led to misinterpretation of test

items and reduced accuracy. In terms of writing, students noted difficulties in maintaining coherence and organization, echoing the challenges highlighted by Tovar Viera et al. (2024) in their study on essay writing.

Alongside these barriers, the study also explored strategies that learners used to address their difficulties. The use of visualization-based methods—such as graphic organizers, pictorial aids, model essay analysis, and pre-writing techniques—emerged as particularly effective. Participants reported that such methods helped them to structure information more clearly, retain key ideas, and improve task performance. For example, graphic organizers supported reading comprehension by enabling learners to map out main ideas and supporting details, while model essay analysis provided a framework for developing logical arguments in writing.

The discussion further highlights the pedagogical implications of these findings. The results confirm Nation's (2009) claim that skills training requires systematic support through strategies. In this context, visualization can serve as an accessible and practical tool for enhancing learning efficiency. Moreover, the integration of visual methods not only addresses existing barriers but also increases learner motivation and engagement, aligning with global trends in modern methodology. These findings suggest that greater emphasis should be placed on incorporating visual techniques into the teaching of receptive and productive skills in EFL classrooms across Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

The study revealed that EFL learners from Termiz, Karshi, and Guliston State Universities face noticeable barriers in both receptive and productive skills, primarily due to vocabulary limitations and lack of practice. At the same time, a considerable number of students expressed positive attitudes toward the use of visual techniques as potential tools to overcome these challenges. Although the effectiveness of visualization has not yet been empirically tested, the findings provide a strong basis for conducting further experimental research to validate its role in enhancing language learning outcomes.

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